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Use Of Information And Communications Technology (ICT) In Teaching Business Studies In Public Secondary Schools In Asaba Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis. Three research questions were developed in line with the objective to guide the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised of forty two (42) business studies teachers in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis. There was no sample since the population is manageable. A structured questionnaire titled "Use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Teaching Business Studies Questionnaire" (UICTTSBQ) was used to collect data from the respondents. The instrument was validated by three experts in Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba. The instrument yielded a reliability result of 0.83 when analyzed using Spearman's rank correlation, indicating that the instrument was reliable. The data was collected by the researcher and two experienced research assistants. Mean and standard deviation statistical analysis were used to analyze the data retrieved from the respondents. Finding reveals that information and communications technology (ICT) facilities are not available for teaching business studies, utilizing information and communications technology (ICT) facilities in teaching has a lot of benefits and there are challenges in the application of information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in Public Secondary Schools in Asaba Metropolis. It was recommended among others that ICT facilities should be made available so as to enable teachers to utilize them in teaching processes. Also, for those who are not computer literate, a training session should be arranged for them so as to be able to apply computers in their teaching processes.

Keywords: ICT, Teaching, Business Studies, Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world today, functional education provides the basic instrument for gainful employment, personality progress, economic prosperity, and moral development built up, and positive interpersonal relationships; while a lack of it signifies ignorance, underdevelopment, maladjustment, crime, poverty, frustration, among others. Effective teaching may be unavoidable without functional teaching with the help of information and communication technology (ICT) to enhance innovative production in modern fields such as science and technology, business studies among others (Bukoye, 2018).

Business studies is an integral part of general education that is concerned with education for business and education about business. According to Okute (2016), business studies is an academic subject that helps students to be exposed to the realities of business practices. The subject is designed to introduce students to the foundational knowledge of the principles and practices of business. Nwobu (2015) stated that

business studies help students to make informed decisions in everyday business of living. Business studies prepare students for business occupations or enable those who are already in the occupation to become more competent and advance to higher business positions. Teaching business studies in secondary schools requires the appropriate use of information and communication technology (ICT).

ICT stands for information and communication technologies. ICT refers to technologies that provide access to information through communications. It is similar to information technology (IT), but primarily focused on communications technologies. This includes the internet, wireless network, cell phones and other communications media". In the past few decades, information and communications technologies have provided society with a vast array of new communication capabilities (Balash, Yong & Bin-Abu, 2018). It was on the basis of this that Abdulla, Al-Hawaj and Twizell (2016) observed that the use of ICT in teaching and learning is critical to make learners learn better and teachers to teach well. It ensures transactional instructional communication where the teacher manages the human materials, time and space to make sure that instructional conditions help in drawing students' attention to stimulation and recall stimulus, thereby improving performance (AlAmmary, 2017). No doubt ICT enables students to learn faster, remember longer, gain more accurate information and receive and understand delicate concepts. The use of ICT in schools includes computers, internet facilities, audio-visual devices, multimedia projectors etc. Computers and internet facilities are now in place in many institutions of learning. It is expected that educators will see ICT as a major teaching and learning device across all educational institutions. Kosoko-Oyedeko and Tella (2018) have shown that with the power of interactivity and participation of multimedia and communication devices, the computer proves an excellent tool for the teaching and learning of school subjects.

Onwuka (2015) opined that teaching is a process of making an impression on passive students, hammering in the facts. The preoccupation of teachers involved in this method is to hand over to the students whatever the teachers themselves received from others. Teaching is an attempt to bring about desirable changes in learner behaviour and reflects the expected behaviour needed to improve the learner and the society where they live. Teaching is sometimes instructing, explaining or telling (Abdulla, Al-Hawaj & Twizell, 2016). The use of ICT in the teaching and learning process seems to be more important and requires more than looking only at the curricula. Information and Communications Technology-driven change in education have been piecemeal and very uneven in its impact; change has been characterized not by revolution but by gradualism (Mogbo, 2012).

Teaching has gone beyond the teacher standing in front of a group of students and disseminating information to them without the students' adequate participation. The researcher posits that with the aid of ICT, teachers can take students beyond traditional limits, ensure their adequate participation in the teaching and learning process and create vital environments to experiment and explore this new development is a strong indication that the era of teaching without ICT skills are gone. Any teacher with adequate and professional skills in ICT utilization will definitely have his students perform better in classroom learning (Alozie, 2017). ICT has contributed a lot to teaching. Aminoke (2015) noted that various contributions and uses of ICT show that it empowers students and allows them access to the discipline, and ICT tools in use include games, simulation, testing, database containing educational data, graphical packages to display education products, spreadsheets and tools for local area network and internet. Each provides the student with opportunities to think differently, have better achievement and increased performance. Teachers need to use ICT skills in order to collect, store, edit and pass information in various forms.

With the emergence of Information and Communications Technology, teaching has changed from traditional chalkboard to electronic learning requiring such skills as internet browsing, Microsoft Word, PowerPoint, Microsoft Excel and teleconferencing gadgets from teachers and students, to collect, store, edit and pass information in various forms. Nwosu (2016) specifies that the benefits of ICT skills to students are to cover the development of multiple sensory delivery, increased self-expression, and active cooperative learning. A secondary school graduate is supposed to be at the forefront of applying ICT skills in their daily contact, which is geared towards preparing them for higher levels. All these, therefore, form the background to which the study is based on the assessment of the use of information and

communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis.

The rapid development of Information and Communications Technology has transformed human society from the information technology age to the knowledge age (Galbreath, 2015). Information and Communications Technology can be used to improve the quality of teaching and learning through; Preparing individuals for the workplace as Information and Communications Technology has the capacity to prepare the present generation of students for a workplace where computers, the internet and related technologies are becoming more and more ever-present. Technological literacy is the ability to use Information and Communication Technology effectively and efficiently is thus seen as representing a competitive edge in an increasingly globalizing job market (Gates, 2016). Expanding Access to Education: Expanding education is enhanced through access to remote learning resources. With the internet and the World Wide Web, a wealth of learning materials can be accessed from anywhere at any time of the day by unlimited number of people. Thus, teachers and students no longer have to rely solely on printed books and other materials in physical libraries which are limited in quantities for their educational needs (Haddad, 2015)

Transforming the Learning Environment into Learner-Centeredness: Information and Communications Technology supported teaching can promote the acquisition of the knowledge and skills that will empower students for lifelong learning. Gaible and Burns (2015) stated that Information and Communication Technology ensures that students have adequate literacy numeracy and other basic skills. Information and Communications Technology is also presented as enabling teachers and students to engage with learning in new ways, ways that transform their relationship.

Potentially Equalizing Strategy for Developing Countries: Information and Communications Technology have the potential for increasing access to and improving the relevance and quality of education in developing countries. Information and Communications Technology greatly facilitate the acquisition and absorption of knowledge, offering developing countries unprecedented opportunities to enhance educational systems, improve policy formulation and execution and wide the range of opportunities for business and the poor. Information and Communications Technologies (ICTs) have become key tools and have had a revolutionary impact on how we perceive the world and how we live. Today, the place of ICTs in education and the world in general cannot be undermined. Modern day businesses are conducted and facilitated through the use of telephones, fax machines and computer communication networks through the internet. The phenomenon has given birth to the contemporary e-commerce, e-government, e machine, e-banking and e-education among others (Apagu & Wakili, 2015).

Aribasala (2016) posited that ICT are increasingly playing an important role in organizations and in society's ability to produce, access, adopt and apply information. They are however being heralded as the tools for the post-industrial age and the foundations for a knowledge economy due to their ability to facilitate the transfer and acquisition of knowledge. Stressing the importance of the use of ICT in schools. Olorunsola (2017), posited that through ICT, some educational needs have been met; it changes the needs of education as well as the potential processes. The use ICT in the teaching process becomes essential. This is because its adoption by teachers will enhance effective teaching. Issues like good course organization, effective classroom management, self-study collaborative learning, tax-oriented activities, and effective communication between the actors of teaching and learning process and research activities will be enhanced by the use of ICT based technology.

The various ICT facilities which are supposed to be available in the teaching and learning process according to Babajide and Bolaji (2016), Bryers (2014), Bamidele (2016) and Ofodu (2017) include; radio, television, computers, overhead projectors, optical fibres, fax machines, CD-Rom, internet, electronic notice board, slides, digital multimedia, video/VCD machine and so on. It appears some of these facilities are not sufficiently provided for teaching and learning in secondary schools. This might account for why teachers are not making use of them in their teaching. According to Ajayi (2015), the use of these facilities involves various methods which include systematized feedback system, computer-based operation/network, video conferencing and audio conferencing; internet/worldwide websites and computer assisted instruction. It should be stressed that the effective use of the various methods of ICT in

teaching and learning depends on the availability of these facilities and teachers' competences in using them. Regarding the ICT equipment/facilities used in teaching, Tolea and Razvan (2017) have categorized ICT equipment/facilities into four main groups which include: hardware, software, internet equipment/facilities and computer projector.

Hardware are devices used in presenting materials. They include the physical parts of components of a device used by teachers in teaching (Oguzor & Adebola, 2017). They list the hardware equipment/facilities to include; computer system, video system, electronic organizer, electronic copy boards, a plasma screen, iPad, interactive whiteboard, mobile phones.

Software equipment/facilities are collection of computer programs and related data that provide the instructions for telling a computer what to do and how to do it. In others words, software is a conceptual entity which is a set of computer programmes, procedures and associated documentation concerned with the cooperation of data processing system (Adnirin, 2018). Hawkins (2016) listed different types of computer software that can be used by teachers in teaching as; Microsoft office packages, internet explorer, adobe reader, skype, Mavis beacon.

The internet according to Wing (2016) is a new broadcast that can be used in any part of the world in a synchronized way, online or offline, get together text, sound, video and provide services like e-mail, dates transfer, video conferencing among others. it is used in teaching and learning processes and is becoming more usual and common tool. These resources enable teachers/lecturers to post research, assignments, books or journal list references online for easy assessment by the students and others (Yusuf & Onasanya, 2016). The internet equipment/facilities according to Sophia, (2016) could include search engines like google, Wikipedia, AOL search, ask.com, Myspace among others, electronic mail (e-mail), social communities, virtual library, virtual classroom. The major benefits of ICT, according to Newhouse, (2016) include; Individualization of instruction is seen as one of the benefits of ICT as it helps in the individualization of instruction which ordinarily is difficult and, in most situations, impossible to realize. Otuka (2017) posited that ICT provides a more individualized self-spaced and self-directed learning experience. This implies that with the aid of ICT facilities learners have the freedom to learn at their own pace, time and convenience, without a limited environment which means learners can access it from anywhere, and anytime. Higher student engagement level is another benefit as Otuka (2017) highlighted that when they integrate ICT in their classrooms, they grab the attention of students that are in their turn using these tools outside in their regular lives. Furthermore, educational technology aids teachers deliver diversified instruction to a larger number of students.

ICT creates sufficient ways for cordial collaboration among students and teachers, irrespective of the distance between them. It makes collaboration among them easier and facilitative. The use of online environment make teaching and learning easier and often more pleasurable and it also afford them the opportunities to exchange instructional ideas without facial contact. Through ICT equipment/facilities, quality education is make affordable and obtainable; the teacher can share their ideas and knowledge across border thereby allowing learners to attend classes notwithstanding, the geographical and economical boundaries (Otuka, 2017). Information and Communications Technology can promote the acquisition of the knowledge and skills that will empower students for lifelong learning. Computers and internet technologies enable new ways of learning which include active learning, collaborative learning, creative learning, evaluative learning and integrative learning. Information and Communications Technology allow a shift from a teacher centered pedagogy and enable learners to explore and discover rather than merely listen and remember (Gaible & Burns 2015).

Other benefits of ICT in teaching and learning as outlined by Odili (2016) are as follows, convenient due to minimal disruption of family and work life, Elimination of space time and geographical constraints, Increased interaction with more accessible teachers with decreased feedback turn-around time, Increased peer interaction due to a collaborative rather than competitive learning environment, Increased quality of learning with deeper critical reflection and systematic scaffolding of ideas taking place.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the recognized importance of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) in education, its integration into the teaching of Business Studies in public secondary schools in Asaba Metropolis remains inadequate. Business Studies, which requires a practical and interactive teaching approach, is still largely taught using traditional methods that limit student engagement and hinder the development of digital and entrepreneurial skills. Although the National Policy on Education (2014) encourages the incorporation of ICT in the curriculum, implementation at the grassroots level has been inconsistent.

In Asaba Metropolis, there is limited evidence on the availability and effective use of ICT tools in teaching Business Studies. Challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, insufficient teacher training, unstable electricity supply, and limited funding have further hindered ICT adoption. This gap between policy and practice raises key questions about the extent of ICT usage, its benefits to teaching and learning, and the barriers preventing effective integration. Consequently, this study aims to assess the use of ICT in teaching Business Studies in public secondary schools within Asaba Metropolis.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is the assessment of the use of information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to find out;

1. Information and communications technology (ICT) facilities available for teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis.
2. The benefits of utilising information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis.
3. The challenges in the application of information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study;

1. What are the information and communications technology (ICT) facilities available for teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis?
2. What are the benefits of utilizing information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis?
3. What are the challenges in the application of information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis?

METHODOLOGY

A survey research design was adopted as a plan of action in the conduct of the study. According to Fowler (2012), survey design is a research design that is used to collect detailed functional information that describes the existing phenomena with a focus on people, their beliefs, behaviours, and the interrelation of sociological and physiological variables. The adoption of this design was informed by its efficient way of collecting information about the population of interest, ease of administration of the research instrument (questionnaire), which can be tailored to the problem the researcher is studying. The population of the study comprised of all business studies teachers in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis. According to information gotten from field survey, there forty-two (42) business studies teachers in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis. The entire population will be used for the study as such, there was no sampling. The table below shows the names of schools and the population.

Table 1: Sample Distribution

S/N	Name of Schools	No. of Teachers
1	Afadia College Asaba	2
2	Asagba Mixed Secondary School, Asaba	4
3	Government Model Secondary School, Asaba	6
4	Isioma Onyeobi College, Asaba	2
5	Niger Mixed Secondary School, Asaba	4
6	Osadenis Mixed Secondary School, Asaba	6
7	West-End Mixed Secondary School, Asaba	6
8	Zappa Basic Secondary School Asaba	4
9	Zappa Mixed Secondary School Asaba	6
10	Women Affairs Secondary School Asaba	2
Total		42

Source: Field Survey (2025)

A structured questionnaire titled “Use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Teaching Business Studies Questionnaire (UICTTQ)” was used to get information from the respondents. The questionnaire was made up of two parts. Part A was used to collect information on the personal data of the respondents, while Part B contained items for answering the three research questions. The numerical value of the scale points (Response modes) is as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point. The questionnaire was validated by two experts at Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba. They were requested by the researcher to vet the items for appropriateness and ambiguity and based on their recommendations, necessary corrections will be made on the instrument to bring it to its final state. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument, a test-retest method was used to administer the instrument twice to 15 business studies teachers in Ibusa, who were not part of the study. Spearman’s Rank Correlation was used to analyze the data, and a coefficient of 0.83 was obtained and which indicated that the instrument was reliable. Validated copies of the questionnaires were distributed to the teachers by the researchers. The researchers ensured that all copies of the instrument administered were adequately collected. The data collected from the respondents will be used for data analysis. Data collected from respondents was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The decision rule for the research questions was based on the mean score, which was set at 2.50. Therefore, any mean scores of the respondents’ statements which rated 2.50 and above were regarded as agree, while mean scores of the respondents’ statements which rated below 2.50 were regarded as disagree.

RESULTS

The section focuses on the analysis of the presentation of data collected from the questionnaire administered. The responses given to each research question were interpreted using mean and standard deviation.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: *What information and communications technology (ICT) facilities are available for teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis?*

Table 2: Mean Response on Availability of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) Facilities for teaching business studies in public secondary schools (N = 42)

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	S.D	Decision
1	There are enough computers/laptops for teaching	4	9	17	12	2.05	0.87	Disagree
2	Television sets are available for teaching	3	8	18	13	2.02	0.83	Disagree
3	Digital library are usually available for teaching	4	9	19	10	2.19	0.85	Disagree
4	CD-ROM, flash drives containing E-journals and e-books are available for teaching	5	11	15	11	2.26	0.89	Disagree
5	Audio recorder/player are available for teaching	4	10	17	11	2.12	0.91	Disagree
6	Printer/photocopier are available for producing hard copies of materials for teaching	2	8	20	12	1.95	0.82	Disagree
7	Interactive white boards/Electronic board are used for teaching	4	10	19	9	2.14	0.74	Disagree
8	There are projectors are available for teaching	3	9	18	12	2.00	0.80	Disagree
9	Public address systems are available for teaching	4	10	17	11	2.10	0.83	Disagree
10	Internet facilities are available for teaching	5	11	15	11	2.21	0.88	Disagree
Grand Mean						2.10	0.83	Disagree

Source: Field Work (2025)

Results presented in Table 2 from the respondents showed that items 1 to 10 scored below 2.50 of the acceptable mean score, which showed that the respondents disagreed with the statements. The grand mean of 2.10, which is also below 2.50 of the acceptable mean score, showed that the respondents reacted negatively to the statements, which revealed that information and communications technology (ICT) facilities are not available for teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis.

Research Question 2: *What are the benefits of utilizing information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis?*

Table 3: Mean Response on the benefits of utilizing information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools (N = 42)

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
11	ICT ensures the individualization of instruction in the study	9	22	9	2	2.93	0.79	Agree
12	It is flexible and convenient for both students and teachers	11	20	8	3	3.00	0.76	Agree
13	Enhance ICT skills and competences of teachers and students	10	23	7	2	3.05	0.78	Agree
14	Enhancement of the teaching strategies of teachers	12	22	6	2	3.10	0.70	Agree
15	It helps students become interested in teaching	8	21	10	3	2.93	0.81	Agree
16	It improves students' understanding	10	23	8	1	3.07	0.75	Agree
17	It improves the quality of teachers	9	22	9	2	2.95	0.72	Agree
18	It transforms the learning environment into learner-centeredness	11	21	8	2	3.05	0.70	Agree
19	It makes teachers continue research on how to teach better	10	22	8	2	3.02	0.78	Agree
20	It helps students to research every aspect	8	20	11	3	2.88	0.79	Agree
Grand Mean						2.99	0.76	Agree

Source: Field Work (2025)

Results presented in Table 3 from the respondents showed that items 11 to 20 scored above 2.50 of the acceptable mean score, which showed that the respondents agreed with the statements. The grand mean of 2.99, which is also above 2.50 of the acceptable mean score, showed that the respondents reacted positively to the statements, which revealed that utilizing information and communications technology

(ICT) facilities in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis has a lot of benefits.

Research Question 3: *What are the challenges in the application of information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis?*

Table 4: Mean response on Challenges in Application of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) business studies in Teaching in public secondary schools (N = 42)

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
21	Lack of a steady electricity power supply	20	17	5	0	3.30	0.63	Agree
22	Insufficient number of qualified teachers	17	16	7	2	3.25	0.77	Agree
23	High cost of ICT facilities	16	17	8	1	3.20	0.80	Agree
24	Lack of a standby generator to forestall a power outage	18	17	6	1	3.26	0.71	Agree
25	Limited access to the internet and slow internet connections	20	18	4	0	3.33	0.70	Agree
26	Lack of adequately equipped ICT centers	17	18	6	1	3.21	0.76	Agree
27	Lack of training for lecturers to update their ICT skills	19	17	5	1	3.28	0.69	Agree
28	Lack of maintenance of ICT facilities	18	17	6	1	3.27	0.73	Agree
29	Lack of professionals to operate ICT facilities	20	17	5	0	3.35	0.69	Agree
30	Lack of funds to purchase needed ICT facilities	18	18	5	1	3.23	0.63	Agree
Grand Mean						3.27	0.71	Agree

Source: Field Work (2025)

Results presented in Table 4 from the respondents showed that items 21 to 30 scored above 2.50 of the acceptable mean score, which showed that the respondents agreed with the statements. The grand mean of 3.05 showed that the respondents reacted positively to the statements, which revealed that there are challenges in the application of information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of research question one showed that information and communications technology (ICT) facilities are not available for teaching business studies in public secondary schools in the Asaba metropolis. As stated in the items, it was discovered that computers/laptops, television sets, digital library, CD-ROM, flash drives containing e-journals and e-books, audio recorder/player, printer/photocopier, interactive white boards/electronic board, projectors, public address systems, and internet facilities are not available in teaching in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis. The findings conform to the findings of Clever (2009), which revealed that there was a serious problem in the availability and utilization of ICT facilities for teaching.

Secondly, the finding from research question two reveals that the utilization of information and communications technology (ICT) facilities in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis. Based on the analysis, it was observed that ICT ensures individualization of instruction, it is flexible and convenient for both students and teachers, enhances ICT-skills and competences of teachers and students, enhancement of teaching and learning. This finding relates to the assertion of Otuka (2017), who posits that ICT provides a more individualized, self-paced, and self-directed learning experience. This implies that with the aid of ICT facilities, learners have the freedom to learn at their own pace, time, and convenience, without a limited environment, which means learners can access it from anywhere, and at any time. Furthermore, Jihan (2015) asserted that ICT also allows learners more autonomy, more cooperative learning, while individualizing information and resources related to the students' needs and interests, all of which can help secure higher student engagement levels. The researcher therefore concluded that with ICT in teaching and learning is made easy, for example,

using the public address system, lecturers do not have to shout for the students to hear them and students sitting behind will hear all the lecturers have to say.

Finally, findings from research question three reveal that there are challenges in the application of information and communications technology (ICT) in teaching business studies in public secondary schools in Asaba metropolis. It was observed that lack of standby electricity power supply, insufficient number of qualified teachers, high cost of ICT facilities, lack of standby generator for forestall power outage, limited access to internet and slow internet connection, lack of adequate equipped ICT facilities, lack of training for lecturers to update their ICT skills, lack of maintenance of ICT facilities, lack of professionals to operate ICT facilities and lack of fund to purchase needed ICT facilities are the challenges facing the application of ICT in secondary schools. This finding conforms with the findings of Okute (2016), which revealed that several challenges hinder effective adoption of ICT in teaching, and the challenges include lack of access to the internet, lack of access to ICT hardware and software facilities, such as computers, multimedia projectors, among others

CONCLUSIONS

Information and communications technology (ICT) seem to have a reflective impact on teaching processes in secondary schools by offering new possibilities for teachers and students. These possibilities can have an impact on teaching and learning processes. This study therefore concludes that ICT facilities in general are not available in teaching and learning, despites its benefits there are challenges such as lack of steady power supply, insufficient number of qualified lecturers, high cost of ICT facilities, lack of professionals to operate ICT facilities, limited access to internet and slow internet connection, lack of well adequately equipped ICT facilities and lack of standby generator to fore stall power outage among others in teaching business studies in Public Secondary Schools in Asaba Metropolis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made

1. ICT facilities should be made available to enable teachers to utilize them in lecturing processes. Also, for those who are not computer literate, a training session should be arranged for them so as to be able to apply computers in their teaching processes.
2. The government should provide adequate funds for secondary schools to enable them to procure necessary relevant ICT facilities for teaching processes.
3. An alternative source of electricity should be arranged to enable the smooth running of the ICT facilities.

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